

interatomic distances nor the coordination numbers. In principle, one can get the desired results by solving the integral equation

$$Q(\vec{x}) = \int \zeta(\vec{y}) \zeta(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) d\vec{y} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $\zeta(\vec{x})$ is the density function of the substance investigated. This equation can be solved uniquely for bounded structures with centre of symmetry or antisymmetry⁷. But the results depend sensitively on the boundary values of the $Q(\vec{x})$ -function which is obtained by the inverse Fourier transformation of the intensity function. In practice, $Q(\vec{x})$ cannot be obtained accurately and the uncertainties involved are extremely difficult (if at all possible) to estimate exactly. The conventional method of analysis of RDF is in principle wrong and consequently the relevant structural data obtained are of doubtful value. The method suggested in ref. 5 ch. XVI is valid for one dimensional cases and is also likely to lead to erroneous conclusions for actual liquids. In this note a new method of analysis of RDF of liquids has been suggested under the assumption that the liquid-arrangement has resulted from the corresponding ideal crystalline structure in consequence of the distortions of the fundamental vectors.

For isotropic substances and for simple liquids the distribution function of each atom in relation to its own neighbours is statistically the same and consequently the expression (1) is valid for all such systems and further in such cases only one function, for example,

$$H_1(r) = \frac{1}{(\pi\alpha^2)^{3/2}} \exp -r^2/\alpha^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

properly shifted would give rise not only to

$$H_{100}(\vec{x}), H_{010}(\vec{x}), H_{001}(\vec{x}) \text{ but also to any } H_p(\vec{x})$$

with the help of (1). Thus,

$$H_p(\vec{x}) = H_{p_1 p_2 p_3}(\vec{x}) = H_{q_1 q_2 q_3}(\vec{x}) \equiv H_q(\vec{x})$$

$$= \frac{1}{(\pi m \alpha^2)^{3/2}} \exp -\frac{1}{m \alpha^2} [(x_1 - q_1 a_1)^2 + (x_2 - q_2 a_2)^2 + (x_3 - q_3 a_3)^2] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{where } m = |p_1| + |p_2| + |p_3| - 1.$$

(q_1, q_2, q_3) are the coordinates of the p th atom in terms of the fundamental crystal lattice vectors a_1, a_2, a_3 at 0°K and (p_1, p_2, p_3) are its coordinates in terms of the first neighbours.

Now, due to the random orientations of the crystallites, in liquids the distribution function for the p th neighbour at a given distance r must be a spherically symmetrical function. This is easily achieved by convoluting the function $H_p(\vec{x})$ given in (4) shifted to the origin, i.e., the function

$$G_p(r) = \frac{1}{(\pi \Delta^2)^{3/2}} \exp -(r^2/\Delta^2); \quad (\Delta^2 = m \alpha^2) \quad \dots (5)$$

with a normalized shell function

$$S(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi r_0^2} \cdot \delta(r-r_0) \quad \dots (6)$$

where δ is Dirac's delta function, $r = |\vec{x}|$ and

$$r_0 = |q_1\vec{a}_1 + q_2\vec{a}_2 + q_3\vec{a}_3| \quad \dots (7)$$

Thus the normalized spherically symmetrical distribution function for the location of the centroid of the p th atom is given by

$$H_p(r) = G_p(r) * S(r) \\ = \frac{1}{4\Delta r_0 \pi^{3/2}} \frac{1}{r} \{ \exp-(r-r_0/\Delta)^2 - \exp-(r+r_0/\Delta)^2 \} \quad \dots (8)$$

Further, we will have to consider all the atoms with the (crystal) coordinates (q_1, q_2, q_3) which occur at the same radial distance r_0 given by (7). Consequently, if r denotes the distance of the n th neighbour from the origin,

$$K_n H_n(r) = \sum_p H_p(r) \quad \dots (9)$$

where the sum is to be extended for all values of p i.e., the corresponding q 's consistent with (7). $H_p(r) \equiv H_q(r)$ is then expressed in terms of only $H_1(r)$ and the total number of its convolution products. Both m and the number of terms s in (9) i.e., the total number of particles at the fixed radial distance r_0 can be calculated exactly from the known crystal structure data. It might be noted that the spherically symmetrical radial distribution function for the n th neighbour $H_n(r)$ as given by (9) is not a Gaussian function but results from the superposition of μ sets of different Gaussian functions (but all spherically symmetrical), the number of each set being determined by the number of crystallographically equivalent positions for the atom q_1, q_2, q_3 , (cf eqns. 8 and 9).

Consequently, one has to determine only $H_1(r)$ i.e., only α by trial and error to fit the given RDF curve. In view of the fact that the first maximum of the RDF determined from experimental results usually lies at a shorter distance than the corresponding value for the crystal structure and that holes and/or fissure might as well arise, in actual practice it might be necessary to alter slightly the mean position of the n th neighbour a_n as well as s , the number of particles at a fixed radial distance $r_0 = a_n$. Eq. (8) shows that RDF would be less sensitive for the variation of s compared to the variations of $r_0 = a_n$ and α . The results of this analysis of RDF of some simple substances near their melting points are being carried out and will be reported later on.